

Climateurope2

Composition and terms of reference of the External Advisory Board (EAB)

Deliverable 8.2

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About Climateurope2

Timely delivery and effective use of climate information is fundamental for a green recovery and a resilient, climate-neutral Europe, in response to climate change and variability. **Climate services address this through the provision of climate information for use in decision-making to manage risks and realise opportunities.**

The market and need for climate information have seen impressive progress in recent years and are expected to grow in the foreseeable future. However, the communities involved in the development and provision of climate services are often unaware of each other and lack interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary knowledge. In addition, quality assurance, relevant standards, and other forms of assurance (such as guidelines, and good practices) for climate services are lagging behind. These are needed to ensure the saliency, credibility, legitimacy, and authoritativeness of climate services, and build two-way trust between supply and demand.

Climateurope2 aims to develop future equitable and quality-assured climate services to all sectors of society by

- Developing standardisation procedures for climate services
- Supporting an equitable European climate services community
- Enhancing the uptake of quality-assured climate services to support adaptation and mitigation to climate change and variability

The project **will identify the support and standardisation needs of climate services, including criteria for certification and labelling, as well as the user-driven criteria needed to support climate action.** This information will be used to propose a taxonomy of climate services, suggest community-based good practices and guidelines, and propose standards where possible. A large variety of activities to support the communities involved in European climate services will also be organised.

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the External Advisory Board (EAB) as part of the management structure of the Climateurope2 project. This body will provide support and guidance on project progress and its alignment with the scope of the topic HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-06 Supporting and standardising climate services.

The objective of this deliverable is to give guidance about the membership, responsibilities and activities developed by this board.

1 Definition

The External Advisory Board (EAB) is a scientific panel whose objective is to ensure the quality of the results of the research activities of the Climateurope2 project.

The Advisory Board members do not have authority to vote on project matters but recommend or give advice to the Climateurope2 consortium.

2 EAB composition and appointment

2.1 EAB composition

The EAB is composed of the following type of experts:

- Horizon Europe external members: the experts belong to external organizations and they are not participating in Horizon Europe projects as coordinators.
- Horizon Europe members: the experts are coordinators of European projects funded by the Horizon Europe Programme.

2.1.1 Horizon Europe external members

- Dr Roger Street, Honorary Research Associate of the Environmental Change Institute (ECI) within the Oxford University.
- Dr Ge Peng, Senior Principal Research Scientist, Earth System Science Center/NASA MSFC IMPACT, University of Alabama in Huntsville.
- Dr Isadora Christel Jiménez, Knowledge and Project area manager of the company Science for Change.

2.1.2 Horizon Europe members

- Dr Giulia Galluccio, Director of ISCD Division, Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC) and coordinator the European project MAGICA- MAXimising the synergy of European research Governance and Innovation for Climate Action (GA 101056920.)
- Dr María José Sanz, Scientific Director, Basque Centre for Climate Change (BC3) and coordinator of the European project MAIA-Maximising impact and accessibility of European climate research (GA 101056935).

2.2 EAB appointment

The Management Board approaches and selects the EAB members considering their expertise and field of experience and trying to have a gender balance among the members.

The membership of the EAB can be extended to other experts if necessary. A new candidate can also be proposed by any of the Climateurope2 partners and approved by the Management Board.

3 EAB tasks

The EAB members' tasks include:

- Ensuring the external evaluation of the project's progress.
- Providing independent advice on new actions and activities in the area by liaising with the Management Board and by participating in the general assemblies.
- Increasing the project's visibility and strengthening its links to international programmes and other activities outside Europe.
- Providing a report with recommendations after each General Assembly of the project and, if needed, upon request from the Climateurope2 Management Board.
 - EAB reports will be taken into account when elaborating deliverables and other project reports.
 - EAB reports will be available in the project wiki under the section "External Advisory Board".
 - EAB reports will be completed according to the template available in Annex 1 of this deliverable.

The EAB will meet at least once per year, either in person or by teleconference taking the advantage of the General Assemblies planned during the project. Extra meetings can be held upon request from any of the EAB members or the coordinator.

In case some of the EAB members cannot attend a meeting, it can be delegated to a substitute chosen by them.

Reimbursement

Climateurope2 has reserved within WP8 funds to support the participation of the EAB in the project general assemblies. Meetings attendance of the EAB shall be covered financially by the Coordinator under WP8 funds.

- Members of the External Advisory Board will not receive an honorarium from the Climateurope2 consortium.
- Reimbursement of travel and accommodation expenses for attending the annual general assemblies can be provided where requested, and if booked according to the Coordinator's travel policy.

4 Annex 1: EAB report template

External Advisory Board report

Report (month X)

Authors:

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The market and needs for climate information has seen impressive progress in recent years and is expected to grow in the foreseeable future. However, the communities involved in the development and provision of climate services are often unaware of each other, and lack interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary knowledge. In addition, quality assurance, relevant standards, and other forms of assurance (such as guidelines, and good practices) for climate services are lagging behind. These are needed to ensure the saliency, credibility, legitimacy and authoritativeness of climate services, and build two-way trust between supply and demand.

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The project will **identify the support and standardisation needs of climate services, including criteria for certification and labelling, as well as the user-driven criteria needed to support climate action.** This information will be used to propose a taxonomy of climate services, suggest community-based good practices and guidelines, and propose standards where possible. A large variety of activities to support the communities involved in European climate services will also be organised.

Two challenges are hence faced by the climate services community: the need to support climate services development through the self-awareness of those who play a role in the market, and the development of methods and criteria that favour the quality assessment of the different components of a climate service to assure that these are trustworthy. This proposal addresses these challenges by developing activities that 1) engage and support the climate services community, taking stock of what has been developed so far, and 2) formulate recommendations to standardise the service practices. **Climateurope2 focuses on the underpinning capability that is required to improve the salience, credibility, legitimacy and usability of current climate services, and also to develop future equitable and quality-assured climate services of greater value to society.**

Executive Summary

Add brief summary of the report

1 External Advisory Board members

Please add the EAB members' name, position and organizations who are contributing to this report.

2 Project opportunities

This section reports the potential opportunities of the project in terms of activities and/or synergies with on-going activities

3 Project risks

This section reports the potential risks that the project might face from the EAB's perspective.

4 Recommendations

5 Conclusions